

Modelling energy demand – A systematic literature review

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<p>Key-Words:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Energy demand modeling – Energy forecasting techniques – Systematic literature survey – Energy demand drivers – Level of detail – Load forecasting – Prediction – Energy demand sectors (residential, commercial, industrial) – Electricity, thermal energy, natural gas 	<p>Abstract:</p> <p>In this article, a systematic literature review of 419 recent publications on final energy demand modelling is provided with a focus on techniques and associated aspects such as accuracy, input data, energy carrier and economic sector as well as the temporal and spatial granularity. This review sheds light into the variety of techniques and use cases of energy demand models; and it serves as a comprehensive literature overview and classification for researchers from both academia and private sector. It enables the readers to identify appropriate literature and data-model-combinations for jump-starting their projects. The analyzed articles have been compiled in comprehensive tables, providing direct access to the respective articles. Individual advantages and drawbacks of techniques, which lead to lower accuracies are discussed as well as common countermeasures. Machine learning techniques are the most popular and are mainly used for electricity forecasting on short temporal horizons and building or regional level, however are dependent on historic load data. Engineering-based models are less dependent on historic consumption data and mostly cover appliance-specific consumption on long temporal horizons. Metaheuristic and uncertainty techniques are used most frequently together with ML techniques to form hybrid models. Statistical well-proven techniques are used in various articles as benchmarks for novel approaches. Accuracy, measured by MAPE, proved to be on similar levels for all techniques. However, higher details in models, e.g. forecasting load of end-use devices, produced lower levels of accuracy compared to forecasts of aggregated loads on regional or country levels.</p>
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Nomenclature:	
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Interference System
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ARCH	Autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity
CI	Computational Intelligence
GIS	Geographic Information System
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
MAPE	Mean Average Percentage Error
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TSA	Time Series Analysis

Content

1	Introduction.....	2
2	Methodology	5
2.1	Preparation.....	5
2.2	Literature search and selection	5
2.3	Data collection.....	6
2.4	Data analysis, classification and interpretation.....	7
3	Classification of techniques	8
3.1	Statistical techniques.....	8
3.2	Machine learning techniques	9
3.3	Metaheuristic techniques.....	9
3.4	Stochastic, fuzzy and grey systems theory techniques	9
3.5	Engineering-based techniques	9
4	Results	10
4.1	Sectors and energy carriers	10
4.2	Techniques and input data	11
4.3	Spatiotemporal level of detail	18
4.4	Prediction accuracy	20
4.5	Measures for improvement of accuracy	22
5	Discussion	23
6	Conclusion	24
7	References	25
	Appendix.....	55
A.1.	Existing literature reviews	55
A.2.	Figures	56

1 Introduction

The transformation of our energy system towards a more reliable, ecofriendly and cost-effective one is a central goal of today’s energy policy. Complex planning processes across different infrastructures involving a variety of stakeholders pave the way for the far-reaching transformation. An integral part of the planning are energy system models which aim to capture the interactions between the elements of our energy system using increasingly detailed and complex algorithms.

Applications of energy system models range from (real time) simulation of energy grid operation to long term infrastructure extension planning and design of decentralized energy communities. Having accurate and detailed information about energy demand in the respective cases is one of the most crucial inputs for such

models and associated decision making processes [1]. Accordingly, there are strong requirements for models representing the demand¹ side regarding their suitability for varying use cases and their accuracy.

As a matter of fact, there is an entire field of research evolving around the question of how energy demand can be modelled using a variety of approaches on different scales ranging from a global level down to a single appliance [2], [3]. In the year 2009, there were 60 English articles indexed on “Web of Science”, which had “energy demand²” and “model” in their title. In 2020 this number had increased to 641. In order to provide reliable energy demand projections, researchers from academia and the private sector have to consider which modelling approach they are going to apply and which inputs are most suitable and available. As the scope of infrastructure models is expanding across multiple infrastructures and energy carriers [4] the demand for models and data with high temporal and spatial resolution is increasing [5]. Growing amounts of smart-meter data in combination with advancements in modelling techniques and computational power are drivers of this development [3].

Energy demand models have a wide range of applications. As shown by Bhattacharyya and Timilsina [6], they can range from short-term energy consumption forecasting in energy grids and markets over simulation of heat and electricity loads in buildings and industrial processes to econometric long-term projections of national energy demand. This article addresses both, future-oriented “forecasting” as well as operational “simulation” of energy demand in technical systems. However, in both cases computational models are the basis, so modelling is the more general term and covers both aspects.

A number of reviews have been published in order to capture the variety of approaches and to describe the developments in energy demand modelling literature. 28 recent reviews have been analyzed for this article. An overview about their characteristics can be found in Table 9 in the appendix. 7 out of these 28 stood out in terms of their systematic procedure, ensuring transparency, replicability and reduced bias according to [3, p. 916 ff.], [7, p. 30 ff.] and [8] and will be briefly presented in the following.

Kuster et al. [9] present a review on electric load forecasting techniques with the intention to provide assistance in the model selection process and identification of best practices. 41 papers are reviewed regarding applied techniques, input data, pre-processing routines, geographic extend, temporal resolution and horizon. While this review covers a variety of criteria, the number of reviewed articles could be extended across other energy carriers and sectors. In [10], 63 articles are reviewed which focus on energy consumption in buildings. They focus on techniques learning from historical/available data for prediction and including support vector machines (SVM), artificial neural networks (ANN) and other machine learning algorithms. The authors analyze the reviewed articles regarding techniques, types of feature, preprocessing, temporal granularity, data size, type of building, type of energy end-use and performance measures. In [11], an analysis of the viability of various model inputs for residential energy consumption is given, focusing on socio-demographic, psychological and contextual factors. In [2], Debnath and Mourshed present a review on forecasting techniques for supply and demand in energy planning models across all energy carriers. The authors present 483 models from articles published between 1985 and 2017. They discuss geographical extend, time frames and performance measures, as well as specific criteria for techniques, such as number of neurons in layers for ANN. While this review provides a wide-ranging analysis, data-related aspects are not included and a distinction between sectors is missing. Riva et al. [12] provide an analysis of 130 peer-reviewed studies on long-term rural energy planning, covering the electricity, oil and heating sector on the demand and supply side. The reviewed studies are classified according to spatial coverage, planning horizon, energy carrier, mathematical models and energy use. Šebalj et al. [13] review 39 articles on predicting natural gas consumption in the residential and commercial

¹ In this article, all methods for the mathematical representation of energy demand or consumption are summarized under the term “energy demand modeling”. Therefore, the terms energy consumption and energy demand are to be understood synonymously.

² The query also included “energy consumption” as a synonym for “energy demand”.

sector, published between 2003 and 2017. Articles are categorized regarding technique, input variables, spatial scope and temporal horizon. Wei et al. [14] compiled a literature study on conventional and artificial intelligence-based models in energy consumption forecasting. 116 publications have been described with respect to purpose, temporal horizons, data properties, applied areas, preprocessing and forecasting techniques. Additionally, forecasting accuracy is evaluated considering the mean average percentage error (MAPE). **Table 1** Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. shows which aspects have been covered by recent systematic reviews. It reveals that none of the existing reviews provides comprehensive coverage regarding all of all of the aspects.

Table 1: Characteristics of recent systematic literature reviews. Overview of recent systematic literature by content. In each line black squares indicate topics covered in the given review. Most reviews cover several sectors or energy carriers and analyze model inputs and spatio-temporal features. Few reviews analyze model accuracies and only the present article covers all the aspects.

Techniques	Energy Carriers				Sectors				Spatio-temporal features			Input data	Accuracy	Articles	Reference
	Electricity	Thermal	Natural Gas	Primary Energy	Residential	Commercial	Industries	General	Temp. Horizon	Temp. Resolution	Spatial Resolution				
■	■							■	■	■			41	[9]	
■	■	■			■							■	n/a	[11]	
■	■	■			■	■	■			■		■	63	[10]	
■	■	■	■	■				■		■		■	483	[2]	
■	■	■			■	■	■		■				130	[12]	
■			■		■	■			■			■	39	[13]	
■	■	■	■	■				■		■		■	116	[14]	
■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■		■	419	This article	

The objective of this review is to provide a systematic and replicable analysis of recent articles on energy demand modelling regarding the utilized techniques as well as associated input data, accuracy and spatio-temporal resolution across different energy carriers and sectors. This comprehensive and concise literature classification serves as a harmonized decision-base for fellow researchers from academia and the private sector who create or use energy demand models. Using this up-to-date knowledge-base, anybody can access the current energy demand modeling literature, browse the most common techniques applied to specific contexts and identify appropriate data-model-combinations with the help of comprehensive and structured tables. Moreover, our review sheds light onto advantages and drawbacks of techniques and shows measures for increasing accuracy in particular contexts as well as corresponding research gaps.

The rest of the article is organized as follows: In section 0, the systematic review process is described. In section 3, a description and classification of techniques is given. In section 4 the results of the literature analysis are presented, starting with sectors and energy carriers and followed by results on modelling techniques, input data, temporal and special characteristics as well as accuracy. In section 5 most significant results are discussed. The paper concludes with section 6.

2 Methodology

The literature review follows a systematic procedure as recommended in [7, p. 30 ff.], [9] and [2]. The step-by-step procedure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Review procedure. The literature review process is divided into four main steps.

2.1 Preparation

The objectives are defined as stated in section 1. The scope of the literature research and eligibility criteria are defined as follows: Firstly, the review is required to be recent, hence publication years are limited from 2015 to 2020. Secondly, articles published in journals related to energy, engineering, modelling and simulation or computer science in English are considered. Thirdly, the articles have to cover energy demand or consumption modelling or forecasting.

The search method is determined to be a single replicable query to an online database of scientific publications. The Web of Science Core Collection is chosen: A well-known database for international journal publications and conference proceedings [15], which allows advanced search options including the use of Boolean operators as well as truncation characters.

2.2 Literature search and selection

In order to compile a list of relevant key words, a preliminary analysis of pertinent publications is conducted through snowball sampling [11], [16] and manual searches in relevant journals. The key words are arranged in three thematic groups referring to “energy”, “demand” and “modelling”, presented in

Table 2. Furthermore, a fourth group is compiled, containing key words that are excluded from the search. This procedure proved to provide a more precise search result.

Subsequently, the search string is derived from the keyword matrix. Keywords in the same group are regarded as substitutes and are linked with an “OR” while key words in different groups are regarded as complementary and are linked with an “AND”. The search is limited to the title (“TI=”) of the publications in order to obtain pertinent results of manageable scope. The exclusion criteria are applied to the title, abstract and author keywords (“NOT TS=”) to increase their impact on the search result. The final search string was applied to the Web of Science Core Collection on the 1st of May 2021 and limited to articles from 2015 to 2020:

(TI=((electric OR "natural gas" OR heat) AND (demand OR consumption OR load OR requirement OR intensity) AND (forecast* OR estimat* OR predict* OR project* OR simulation OR disaggregation OR planning OR model* OR "bottom up" OR "top down")) NOT TS=(storage OR carbon OR emission OR price OR optimization OR vehicle OR climate))*

Table 2: Keyword compilation. Table contains the keywords used for the literature research arranged by thematic groups. Keywords in the bottom cell are explicitly excluded, which leads to a more precise search result. The * is a truncation operator to retrieve words with variant zero to many characters.

Energy	Demand	Modelling
Electric*	Demand	Forecast*
Natural gas	Consumption	Estimat*
Heat	Load	Predict*
	Requirement	Project*
	Intensity	Simulation
		Disaggregation
		Planning
		Model*
		Bottom up
		Top down
Excluded keywords: storage, carbon, emission, price, optimization, vehicle, climate		

The search yielded 695 articles, which were then further scrutinized based on their title and abstract. During the screening process, 276 were excluded due to non-matching topics or closed access despite institutional logins at the publishers’ websites. In total, 419 articles remained.

2.3 Data collection

Articles are analyzed according to a variety of properties, which represent the analysis criteria and are listed in Table 3. Each criterion is specified by a range of possible values. Some criteria have mutual exclusive values, while others do not. In the former case, the values are single-counted while in the latter case double counting may occur. This happens if multiple values are possible for a single criterion, e.g. if electricity as well as natural gas consumption is forecasted in the same article. In some cases, the reviewed articles do not contain enough information to describe a particular criterion. These cases are marked as “not specified”.

The MAPE is defined as the average absolute discrepancy between the predicted value and the actual value, expressed as a percentage of the actual value [17]. It is a unitless performance measure and not dependent on the magnitude of the system, which makes it appropriate for comparing the performance of techniques applied in different contexts [18]. Therefore, it is a widely used accuracy measure in energy demand modeling [3] and is used in this review for statistical evaluation and comparison among techniques and spatio-temporal characteristics.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Table 3: Assessment criteria. Overview of analysis criteria defining the collected data during step 3 of the review procedure. Each item represents a property characterizing the techniques applied in the respective articles. A short description and possible values are given. For mutually exclusive criteria only one value is possible, while for non-exclusive properties multiple values can be given and counted multiple times.

Analysis criteria	Description	Possible values	Mutually exclusive
<i>Technique</i>	Modeling technique applied	Artificial neural network, support vector machine, regression, ARIMA etc.	No
<i>Category of techniques</i>	General category of applied technique	Statistical, machine learning, metaheuristic, stochastic/fuzzy/grey and engineering-based techniques	No
<i>Technique combination</i>	A single technique or a combination of techniques was applied	Stand-alone or hybrid approach	Yes
<i>Model inputs</i>	Inputs for energy demand models serving as explanatory variables and predictors	Data describing historic load, calendar information, weather, economy, demographics, environment, prices, behavior and information about the technical system	No
<i>Energy carrier</i>	Forecasted/modelled type of energy	Electricity, natural gas, energy for heating and cooling	No
<i>Sector</i>	Economic sector or consumer group which is modelled	Industrial, commercial, residential, general	No
<i>Technical system</i>	Applications or technical systems, which is modelled	Power grid, gas grid, district heating, building, production	No
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Spatial level of detail of models	Country, regions (e.g. district), households/buildings, appliances	Yes
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Scale of time steps that are described by the models	Sub-hourly, hourly, daily, above daily	Yes
<i>Temporal horizon</i>	Time span that is covered by the models	Short-term (up to one day), medium-term (several weeks or months), long-term (one year and above)	Yes
<i>Accuracy</i>	Performance evaluation of presented models	Numeric values for MAPE	No

2.4 Data analysis, classification and interpretation

During this step, the collected data is analyzed. Given the variety of entries for each criterion, several classifications are made. Model inputs are divided into seven categories: historic energy demand, weather, calendar, demographic/economic, behavioral, price and technical system data. Spatial resolution refers to the level of detail and is categorized into country, regions, households/buildings and appliances, which refer to end-user devices. Hence, the smallest energy consuming entity, which is separately modelled defines the level of detail and to which category the respective article belongs. E.g. demand models for decentralized mini-grids are assigned to category households/buildings or appliances depending on the level of detail of the models. Temporal resolution is categorized into sub-hourly, hourly, daily and above daily. For the temporal horizon various categorizations exist in the literature. Debnath and Mourshed [2] define short-term as less than 3 years, medium-term as between 3 and 15 years and long-term as more than 15 years. Sieh and Chen [19] distinguish between ultra-short-term (minutes to hours), short-term (one hour to weeks), mid-term (days to one month) and long-term (years). In order to avoid overlapping time spans the following three-part definition was used, inspired by Wei et al. [14]: short-term (up to one day), medium-term (several weeks and months), long-term (one year and above).

For techniques, a variety of classifications can be found in the literature. Debnath and Mourshed [2] distinguish between statistical, computational intelligence (CI) and mathematical programming as well as stand-alone and hybrid techniques. Within the category of statistical techniques they define regression, time series analysis (TSA) and autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) techniques. Within the category of CI they mention machine learning (ML), uncertainty and metaheuristic techniques as well as expert-based methods. Hong and Fang [3] suggest the two general categories of statistical and artificial intelligence techniques, with

the former comprising multiple linear regression and TSA techniques and the latter including ANN, fuzzy regression, SVM and gradient boosting machines. Wei et al. [14] distinguish between conventional techniques, including TSA, regression and grey models, and artificial intelligence techniques, such as ANN and SVM. Kuster et al. [9] discuss the categories of TSA, regression models, ANN, SVM and bottom-up techniques.

This article is based on the classification by Debnath and Mourshed [2], however extended by engineering-based techniques, which have been mentioned by other authors and referred to as bottom-up techniques [6], [9], [20]–[23]. Expert-based systems and mathematical programming mentioned in [2] are not considered since none of the analyzed articles followed either approach. Furthermore, the category of uncertainty techniques, which consists of fuzzy logic and grey models according to [2], is complemented by stochastic models, such as simulations with Markov chains or Gaussian processes, which have been encountered several times during data collection. The category name “uncertainty technique” might evoke some ambiguity amongst readers, since uncertainty is a natural property of any forecasting attempt. Therefore the category name is renamed into “stochastic/fuzzy/grey systems theory”. The classification used in this article consists of statistical (including regression and TSA), ML, metaheuristic, stochastic/fuzzy/grey, and engineering-based techniques, which can be combined to form hybrid approaches across categories. A detailed description is presented in the following chapter.

After classification and analysis the results are presented using bar-plots and box-plots as well as structured tables for direct accessibility of articles. Subsequently, highlights are discussed regarding particular advantages and drawbacks of techniques.

3 Classification of techniques

Given the variety of techniques available for modeling and forecasting energy demand a description for each category is needed. Based on the classifications of [2], [9] (see section 2.4) the following five categories are defined: Statistical, ML, metaheuristic, stochastic/fuzzy/grey, and engineering-based techniques.

3.1 Statistical techniques

According to [2] and [3] this category consists of regression and TSA techniques. As shown in [6], techniques from this category have been used in econometrics to explore the interrelationship between energy demand and economic development.

Regression techniques are used to solve an underlying regression problem [24, p. 13], which consists of finding an approximation of a functional relation between numerical input and output variables. To find a solution for the approximation different methods are employed, oftentimes minimizing the sum of the squares of errors [25]. For linear relations this can be done by the ordinary least squares method. For non-linear relation methods of steepest descent are used [25] or kernel functions [26]. Typical examples for statistical regression as found among the reviewed articles are linear, nonlinear, logistic, quantile and ridge regression. Outside of statistical techniques, non-parametric regression can be found within where ML techniques, such as ANN, kernel regression or regression trees are employed to derive the functional form and regression parameters from the data [27], [28].

TSA techniques derive their predictions from a historic time series, i.e. historic energy consumption data. In their core, many TSA approaches represent regression models since the predicted value is estimated based on one or more previous values [9, p. 260]. This category includes univariate time series models such as Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA). Popular other techniques are the integrated ARMA (ARIMA) model for non-stationary time series, the SARIMA models for seasonality and ARMAX to include external variables [3], [29]. A typical multivariate TSA method is vector auto-regression as used in [30], [31]. As suggested in [2], the category of TSA also includes exponential smoothing models and autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) techniques.

3.2 Machine learning techniques

Techniques from this category find broad application in energy demand modeling and prediction and can be divided into supervised and unsupervised learning approaches.

Supervised learning approaches use labeled training datasets to derive a function describing a relation between inputs and outputs based on examples of input-output pairs [32, p. 529]. They can be applied to numerical variables in the case of regression problems and categorical variables in the case of classification problems [33]. Within this sub-category, common techniques are ANN, instance-based algorithms, such as k-nearest neighbor and kernel machines [34], such as SVM, which can convert nonlinear problem in low space to a linear problem in high-dimensional space [35]. Furthermore, there are decision trees, Bayesian algorithms and ensemble learning, such as gradient boosting machines [3] in this category.

Unsupervised learning approaches are often applied to clustering problems. These algorithms deduce structures in an unlabeled input dataset, e.g. through finding similarities [36].

3.3 Metaheuristic techniques

Metaheuristic techniques oftentimes are used to solve optimization problems and can be incorporated into other techniques to improve performance [24]. The category includes evolutionary algorithms, which mimic mechanisms that are inspired by biological processes, such as reproduction, mutation, recombination and selection [2, p. 306]. It includes genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, bee colony optimization, firefly algorithms and more [37]. In combination with ML approaches, they can be employed for parameter optimization in SVM [38] or weight optimization in ANN [23], [39], resulting in approaches such as the firefly algorithm neural network [24]. Genetic algorithms are also used for feature selection in ML approaches [40], [41].

3.4 Stochastic, fuzzy and grey systems theory techniques

The techniques in this category are used to model different types of uncertainty. Zimmerman describes two basic forms of uncertainty: The traditional logic of probability describes randomness regarding the occurrence of an event, whereas fuzziness, describes ambiguity of an event, i.e. to what extent an event occurs [42, p. 3]. As Hájek et al. [43] point out, probability and fuzzy logic represent different sorts of uncertainty. Probability theory is used to describe stochastic processes [44] in which future states of a system are described by their past states plus a random change.

In energy demand modeling, stochastic processes such as Markov chains are used for forecasting and simulation of load profiles [21], [45]–[47]. Fuzzy logic is employed in the form of fuzzy time series [48], fuzzy regression models [3], fuzzy clustering [49] and neuro fuzzy interference systems (ANFIS) [50]. Tien states that fuzzy uncertainty can be analyzed with the grey system theory [51] and Debnath and Mourshed classify them as uncertainty methods [2]. The grey theory was proposed by Deng in 1982 and was developed to estimate the behavior of an uncertain system given only a limited amount of data [52]. The fundamental grey model GM(1,1) relies on as few as four recent data points to forecast the future data point [51]. The model uses the least square method to obtain the parameters for the grey differential equations, which describe the change between time steps [52].

3.5 Engineering-based techniques

Engineering-based techniques follow a bottom-up approach and use a variety of external and internal parameters to describe an energy consuming system in high detail [6], [24]. Oftentimes, individual loads of end-use appliances are considered to obtain aggregate profiles [20]. Common examples are models on the level of individual dwellings [53] or industrial processes [54] as well as building simulations [55]. Engineering-based models have proven their worth in planning and design of technical systems, being able to simulate a system's behavior under conditions, for which there has been little historic data recorded yet [22]. Furthermore, they

are promising approaches regarding the inclusion of the effects of household composition and individual behavior of dwellers as well as testing demand side management strategies [21]. While techniques from this category are widely deployed in practice they have been less visible in scientific articles on energy demand modeling and rarely been included into literature reviews.

Geographic information systems (GIS) are used for referencing data to geographic shapes, which have a distinct location and orientation relative to a reference coordinate system. Most of the times they are used for visualization and mapping of energy consumption as well as for urban [56] and rural [57] planning of infrastructure and building simulation [55], [58].

4 Results

A total number of 419 articles originating from 54 different countries was reviewed. The country with the highest output during the last years is China (98) followed by the USA (40) and Turkey (31). The analysis of the publication dates shows a slight increase of articles over the last six years from 66 in 2015 to 77 in 2020.

4.1 Sectors and energy carriers

Figure 2 shows the energy carriers and economic sectors on which the articles were focused. It reveals that in most articles the consumer group is not limited to a single sector but rather comprises all sectors. This is the case when energy consumption of an entire (market-) region is modelled. However, targeted modelling of residential and commercial energy consumption is also common, while industrial consumers are analyzed rather rarely. On the one hand, this could be explained by a lack of publicly available consumption data for the industrial sector, but on the other hand also by a required increased complexity of the required model, since industrial energy consumption tends to be less dependent on exogenous influencing factors (e.g. weather) and shows rather noisy temporal patterns.

Figure 2 also shows that most articles focus on electricity demand. However, particularly within the residential and commercial sector, there are various articles modelling the consumption of thermal energy, i.e. demand for heating and cooling. This can be partially explained by the fact, that there is a significant number of articles focusing on energy in buildings in these sectors, where thermal energy accounts for the largest share of energy consumed. A separate analysis on all technical systems showed that most articles focus on power grids, smart grids and buildings (see Figure 13 in appendix A.2). Furthermore, a deeper look into the results also reveals that 96 % of all reviewed articles focus on a single energy carrier and only very few articles consider more than one energy carrier.

Figure 2: Sectors and energy carriers. The number of published articles is shown by sector and energy carrier. In most articles energy consumption of all sectors is modeled, e.g. of an entire region. Electricity consumption is modeled the most. In residential and commercial sectors, a significant number of articles focus on heating and cooling demand in buildings.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Table 4 compiles the results of the analysis on the general characteristics and allows a direct tracing of the respective references. Fellow researchers can use this overview to find articles, which have similar objects of research with regard to the energy carriers and the sector.

Table 4: Articles sorted by energy carrier and sector. Compiles the results of the analysis on the regarding energy carriers and sectors. And allows for direct tracing of the respective references. Table can be used to find all relevant articles regarding the two analysis criteria.

Energy carrier	Sector	References
Electricity	All sectors	[3], [19], [30], [31], [34], [35], [41], [48], [52], [53], [59]–[158][28], [40], [49], [159]–[189] [190]–[216]
	Residential	[20]–[22], [45], [53], [57], [217]–[290], [291]–[309]
	Commercial	[17], [22], [82], [218], [228], [240], [243], [248], [255], [266], [271]–[273], [277], [279], [286], [310]–[338], [293], [339]–[343]
	Industry	[46], [50], [52], [54], [72], [82], [110], [243], [260], [271], [277], [279], [286], [334], [344]–[350], [351]–[356]
Gas	All sectors	[18], [168], [357]–[370], [371]–[374]
	Residential	[375]–[384], [385]
	Commercial	[328], [375], [376], [378], [381], [383], [386]
	Industry	[351], [381], [383], [386], [387]
Heating/ Cooling	All sectors	[38], [388]–[397]
	Residential	[23], [53], [55], [58], [241], [249], [396], [398]–[417]
	Commercial	[310], [312], [319], [328], [399], [401], [411], [418]–[431]
	Industry	[54], [351], [432]

4.2 Techniques and input data

A variety of techniques is employed in the field of energy demand modelling. Figure 3 shows the number of appearances (n) of each of the five major categories of techniques (see section 3) across all articles as well as the proportion of energy carriers of which the consumption was modelled.

Figure 3: Relative share of energy carrier within each category of techniques. The relative share of appearances of each energy carrier within each of the five major categories of techniques (see section Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.) is shown along with the total number of appearances (n) of each category. Approaches like ML and statistical techniques are used the most and are largely applied to model electricity consumption. These methods mainly rely on historic consumption data, which is particularly well available for electricity consumption. Engineering-based approaches are used less frequently overall but are suited to model heat/cooling demand, especially in the context of building simulation.

It is revealed that ML and statistical techniques are employed in most of the reviewed articles. This can be explained by the fact that ML and a large number of statistical techniques, like TSA, can be applied to a variety of use cases with relatively little effort in terms of model configuration and data preparation. They mainly require historic load data as an input, which can be complemented by a limited set of external parameters, such

as calendar or weather information [52], [59], [60], [163]. Conventional regression techniques, like multiple linear regression, are commonly used as well and also perform as benchmarks for other approaches [217], [310], [311].

Stochastic, fuzzy and grey techniques can be implemented as stand-alone models [220], e.g. simulating load profiles by sampling from stochastic processes such as Gaussian processes or Markov chains [53], [221], [433]. However, the representation of uncertain outcomes through stochastic, fuzzy or grey expressions is also often combined with other techniques such as statistical regression [219], [434] or ANN [62], [97], giving results in the form of membership functions, intervals or probabilistic density.

Metaheuristic techniques are often used as part of hybrid techniques. As their application requires particular expertise, their usage is limited to the number of cases where the additional effort is justified. Typical application is the optimization of model parameters [35], [61] or feature selection [40], [50] in ML models. Another example is the application of genetic algorithms in order to create optimized models as the result of an evolutionary process in which model configuration is refined over multiple generations [164], [181].

In the case of engineering-based techniques, energy demand is derived from the specifications of the system and its technical details [54], [218], [398]. Hence, an accurate simulation with an engineering-based model requires a high amount of data and effort, which reduces the widespread use of such approaches [435]. However, engineering-based techniques are used to a greater extent to model heating and cooling demands, especially in the context of building simulation.

GIS techniques are used to reference data to geo-spatial shapes and visualization in the form of geographical maps. This has been used in the context of building simulation, where geometry and orientation regarding was considered [55], [58], [424], [436] or planning of rural [57] or urban [277], [366] grid infrastructure. In other cases regional loads and trends in spatial energy consumption were analyzed [22], [90], [154], [386] or modeled using socioeconomic data [279], [282], [403].

Figure 3 also highlights that electric energy demand is modelled most frequently above all other energy carriers. This does not come surprising since electricity is the most valuable energy carrier with the widest range of applications. Furthermore, compared to the infrastructures of other energy carriers the electrical grid is associated with more stringent requirements of balancing supply and demand at all times to ensure system stability resulting in great interest for advanced prediction models and data [437]. This trend is also fueled by the ongoing expansion of the metering sector producing increasing amounts of load data [438]. Therefore, we also see a clear domination of electricity within the categories that heavily rely on historic consumption data: ML, statistical and stochastic/fuzzy/grey techniques. In contrast, engineering-based models, which are less dependent on historic load data, are commonly applied to simulate both electric and thermal energy demand.

Figure 4 provides more detail on the ML techniques that are used in the articles. ANNs [63], [388], by far, show the highest number of appearances, followed by instance-based algorithms such as support vector machines (SVM) [64], [98]. Clustering algorithms such as the k-means algorithm are also used frequently to split datasets into groups of maximum similarity. This can be applied to the formation of consumer groups but also to finding similar days in historic load datasets [222], [232], [312]. Bayesian algorithms and decision trees use supervised learning algorithms and therefore also typically used for regression and classification problems, e.g. Bayesian networks [223], [357] or classification and regression trees [165], [399]. Ensemble learning (EL) algorithms combine multiple ML techniques that are individually trained in order to obtain an improved overall performance. This can be achieved by bootstrap aggregating (bagging) [65], [166] and boosting [94], [224].

Figure 4: ML techniques. Number of appearances of each individual technique within the cluster of ML techniques is displayed. Supervised learning with ANN is the predominant ML technique. Clustering algorithms are frequently used for data preparation and feature selection. Decision trees and Bayesian networks are used rather rarely.

Overall, in 210 out of 419 articles a combined approach was employed. Figure 5 shows the combinations among the five main categories. The self-arcs show the number of times the respective technique was used as a stand-alone approach or was combined with a technique from the same category, which is the case for 63 articles within the category of ML, 17 articles with statistical techniques, 3 articles with metaheuristic techniques and respectively 4 articles with stochastic/fuzzy/grey and engineering-based techniques.

Figure 5: Combination of techniques. An arc connects two categories whenever in at least one article combination of techniques from the two categories was used. Self-arcs indicate that a technique was used as a stand-alone or combined with a technique from the same category. The size of the self-arc/arc at its start and end point represents the share of stand-alone/combined techniques relative to the total number of papers. Engineering-based techniques have the highest proportion of stand-alone models and metaheuristic techniques have the highest proportion of hybrid models. ML techniques often form hybrid techniques with themselves as well as with statistical and stochastic/fuzzy/grey techniques.

The analysis shows that all techniques, except engineering-based ones, have a higher proportion of combined applications compared to their stand-alone usage. A typical example for a combined approach is the employment of techniques for clustering or frequency analysis for upstream data preparation. These techniques refine input data, e.g. by signal decomposition through Fourier or wavelet transformation, before

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

the data is fed into a downstream model implemented by TSA [65], [159], [375] or ML techniques [66]–[68], [106], [182], [358], [418], where each of the decomposed signals is predicted separately. Another example is the integration of fuzzy mathematics into ANNs resulting in ANFIS [60], [69], [419], [420] or the incorporation of metaheuristic optimization algorithms into the training stage of an ANN [107], [376] or SVM [35], [38], [61]. Another form of combined models will give an overall result for a prediction as a weighted average of the results of multiple models. Hereby, the calculation of the weights can be subject to various (metaheuristic) optimization techniques, allowing TSA, regression or ML techniques to be combined into one approach [60], [69], [70], [313], [439]. In the case of engineering-based techniques, there are examples of combining simulation results from stochastic processes with bottom-up models, which are predominantly used for predicting energy demand in households [53], [244], [440].

Another aspect of the reviewed articles are the respective datasets that serve as inputs for the models. Table 5 gives an overview of examples for different model inputs, reflecting the variety of input data that is used in the field.

Table 5: Model inputs. Classification of possible data-sets used as model input along with an examples of data-sets.

Model inputs	Examples
Historic energy demand	Historic load, electricity, heating, cooling or natural gas demand
Weather data	Outside temperature, atmospheric pressure, cooling and heating degree days, humidity, solar radiation, wind speed
Calendar data	Time of day, day of week, month, holidays, bridge days, seasons, workday, working hours, operating time of appliance
Demographic or economic data	Economic indicators: GDP, GNI, level of production, income, import and export level of a region demographic indicators: human development indices, population, number of dwellers/ buildings/ residences, age, sex, education, infant mortality
Technical system data	Appliance data: equipment installed, number of appliances, efficiency, material properties, air change ratio, flow rate, outlet/ inlet temperatures, rated power of equipment, impedance Building data: floor space, number of bedrooms, transmission factor, building type, age of building, efficiency rating, geometry of building, status of refurbishment, window area, building material, indoor temperature, indoor humidity
Usage and behavioural data	Time-use survey data, building usage (main residency, rented, owned etc.), occupancy/activity patterns, operation/usage time of a device
Energy prices	Electricity and gas prices, tariffs, payment methods

Figure 6 gives an overview about the frequency of usage of different types of input data as well as an indication of whether they are used in combination with others (“Multiple DD”) or as a “single DD”. It is revealed that historic energy demand is used in 85 % of the articles, which highlights its significance for energy demand modelling. As historic demand can be forecasted by trend extrapolation and pattern recognition, e.g. in the case of ARMA models, it constitutes a stand-alone data source.

Figure 6: Input data – frequency of usage. The number of articles relying on the seven different types of input data is shown. Historic energy demand is one of the most important data-sources, followed by weather and calendar data.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Weather data is used in 43% of the articles. Its frequent use is due to the fact that operational patterns of some end-user devices are correlated with weather phenomena, e.g. heating, cooling and lighting systems. Calendar information is also widely used (29% of the articles), since energy consumption often exhibits regular daily, weekly or annual patterns. For example, the metering data of a company will reflect working hours and operation of technical equipment. Similarly, usage and behavioral data (also referred to as time of use data) describes the relationship between energy consumption and user behavior, i.e. a parameter indicating that a technical device is now in use. Regional demographic and economic data describe properties of a region, which are relevant for the energy consumption on an aggregated scale, ranging from the household income to economic output of a region.

When taking a closer look at the usage of DD across the techniques (Figure 7), it becomes apparent that engineering-based techniques do not rely on historic energy demand data as much as the other techniques. Here, external parameters such as information on the technical system or weather data are essential and historic energy demand is rather used for calibration and validation purposes.

Figure 7: Input data type by method. For each method, the relative share of the seven input data types is shown. Across all methods, engineering-based approaches rely less on historic energy demands.

Table 6 and Table 7 present the results of the analysis on the techniques as well as DD and links each article to its respective property. This classification of articles can be used by fellow researchers in academia and the private sector to find examples of data-model-combinations in recent literature and enables jump-starting their projects. By providing a property-oriented overview, the table reveals research gaps and model-data-combinations, which have been used rarely.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Table 6: Techniques and input data used per article (1/2). Compiled results of the analysis on techniques and input data. Table follows a matrix structure: All articles referenced within a cell rely on the category specified by the corresponding row and the input data specified by the column.

Category of technique	Technique	Historic Energy Demand	Weather data	Calendar data	Demographic or economic data	Technical system data	Usage or behavioral data	Energy prices		
ML	ANN	[19], [22], [41], [46], [49], [50], [52], [59], [60], [62], [63], [66], [67], [69], [70], [73], [76], [84], [86], [94], [97], [100], [102], [105], [107], [109]–[112], [117], [120], [121], [126], [127], [129], [131]–[133], [135], [136], [141], [147], [148], [151], [152], [154], [158], [162]–[167], [169], [170], [179]–[182], [184], [219], [224], [228], [230], [248], [251], [255], [257], [258], [261], [263], [265], [269], [272], [274], [275], [278], [280], [288], [312], [316], [320], [321], [324], [328], [330], [332], [333], [336], [357], [358], [361], [362], [365], [366], [376], [382], [388], [390], [392], [399], [401], [402], [404], [407], [419], [420], [423], [428], [441]–[444]	[22], [23], [41], [62], [66], [70], [76], [86], [94], [97], [100], [102], [105], [120], [121], [127], [129], [132], [133], [135], [146], [147], [154], [162], [170], [219], [224], [228], [230], [248], [257], [257], [258], [265], [272], [274], [275], [312], [316], [324], [327], [330], [332], [333], [336], [358], [361], [365], [366], [368], [382], [388], [390], [392], [395], [399], [401], [404], [407], [419], [420], [423], [428], [442], [443]	[49], [62], [63], [66], [69], [70], [73], [76], [84], [86], [94], [102], [105], [112], [121], [129], [133], [162], [166], [179], [181], [182], [184], [228], [248], [251], [257], [257], [258], [263], [320], [357], [358], [388], [390], [392], [395], [399], [401], [404], [419], [420], [423], [428], [442], [443]	[22], [41], [50], [100], [120], [124], [141], [151], [154], [257], [278], [312], [324], [327], [368], [361], [365], [366], [368], [382], [390], [392], [395], [399], [401], [404], [419], [420], [423], [428], [442], [443]	[22], [41], [50], [100], [120], [124], [141], [151], [154], [257], [278], [312], [324], [327], [368], [361], [365], [366], [368], [382], [390], [392], [395], [399], [401], [404], [419], [420], [423], [428], [442], [443]	[22], [41], [50], [100], [120], [124], [141], [151], [154], [257], [278], [312], [324], [327], [368], [361], [365], [366], [368], [382], [390], [392], [395], [399], [401], [404], [419], [420], [423], [428], [442], [443]	[23], [140], [154], [219], [224], [263], [278], [312], [324], [327], [368], [361], [365], [366], [368], [382], [399], [402], [408], [410], [423], [432]	[41], [120], [224], [257], [327], [368], [361]	[50], [100], [224], [361]
	Instance Based	[34], [35], [38], [40], [61], [64], [67], [68], [76], [80], [85], [98], [105], [129], [150], [154], [161], [219], [238], [248], [255], [258], [265], [270], [276], [317], [319], [321], [359], [382], [391], [393], [399], [418], [445]	[38], [40], [64], [76], [105], [129], [150], [154], [219], [248], [258], [265], [317], [382], [391], [393], [395], [399], [418]	[40], [68], [76], [85], [105], [129], [238], [248], [258], [317], [359], [391], [395], [399], [445]	[35], [64], [80], [124], [154], [161], [238], [265], [399], [418], [445]	[38], [154], [219], [319], [391], [399], [408], [418]	[80], [238]			
	Clustering	[22], [49], [50], [70], [79], [83]–[85], [90], [106], [129], [139], [150], [153], [154], [222], [225], [226], [231], [232], [234], [251], [262], [264], [269], [284], [287], [312], [315], [326], [348], [362], [419], [442]	[22], [70], [129], [146], [150], [154], [222], [232], [257], [262], [312], [419], [442]	[49], [70], [84], [85], [106], [129], [222], [231], [232], [251], [257], [419]	[22], [50], [79], [83], [90], [154], [232], [262], [312], [315]	[154], [232], [262], [312], [315]	[257], [315]	[50]		
	Ensemble Learning	[65], [66], [94], [112], [121], [148], [165], [166], [224], [264], [272], [274], [313], [332], [336], [370], [391], [419], [442]	[65], [66], [94], [121], [224], [272], [274], [332], [336], [391], [419], [442]	[65], [66], [94], [112], [121], [166], [313], [391], [419]	[370]	[224], [391], [410]	[224]	[224]		
	Deep learning	[22], [66], [76], [109], [133], [135], [152], [164], [179], [181], [228], [261], [275], [278], [280], [365], [444]	[22], [66], [76], [133], [135], [228], [275], [365], [368]	[66], [76], [133], [179], [181], [228], [275]	[22]	[278]	[368]			
	Bayesian algorithms	[40], [110], [113], [223], [275], [330], [333], [357], [392]	[40], [88], [223], [254], [275], [330], [333], [392]	[40], [88], [223], [275], [392]	[254], [357]	[140], [254]	[223]	[223]		
	Decision trees	[75], [165], [332], [387], [399], [426]	[332], [387], [399], [426]	[75], [387], [399], [426]	[387], [399], [426]	[399], [408], [426]				

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Table 7: Techniques and input data used per article (2/2). Continuation of Table 6.

		Historic Energy Demand	Weather data	Calendar data	Demographic or economic data	Technical system data	Usage or behavioral data	Energy prices
Statistical	Regression	[17], [28], [31], [70], [77], [78], [83], [88], [89], [92], [93], [95], [96], [99], [100], [116], [120], [121], [128], [129], [139], [141], [144], [148], [151], [155], [157], [161], [171], [172], [177], [178], [217], [218], [224], [229], [233], [235], [236], [238], [245], [246], [248], [250], [253], [265], [266], [272], [273], [279], [281], [282], [286], [310]–[312], [315], [318], [319], [321]–[323], [325], [329], [329], [332], [335], [338], [369], [370], [378]–[380], [382], [387], [389], [392], [401], [403], [421], [423], [426], [446]	[272], [279], [281], [332], [382], [395]	[395]	[141], [144], [151], [265]	[267], [335], [409], [410]	[120], [224], [233], [237], [282], [311], [315], [322], [323]	[100], [155], [224], [238], [311], [379], [409]
	TSA/ ARCH	[17], [30], [31], [40], [48], [49], [60], [65], [69], [74], [78], [80], [81], [89]–[91], [96], [103], [104], [106], [108], [110], [112]–[114], [118], [122], [125], [127], [129]–[131], [137], [142]–[144], [149], [156], [158], [159], [162], [163], [169], [172], [175], [180], [185], [188], [227], [236], [240], [247], [251], [252], [255], [265], [272], [277], [281], [284], [286], [288], [313], [321], [326], [332], [338], [344], [345], [348], [350], [364], [375], [383], [444], [446], [447]	[40], [65], [96], [118], [125], [127], [129], [130], [162], [172], [175], [236], [247], [252], [265], [272], [281], [332], [345], [364]	[40], [49], [65], [69], [74], [78], [91], [96], [103], [106], [112], [129], [162], [172], [175], [251], [252], [313], [344]	[30], [80], [89]–[91], [104], [144], [265], [383]	[247]	[80], [91], [104]	
Uncertainty	Stochastic	[21], [28], [30], [31], [34], [35], [41], [45], [46], [73], [75], [87], [96], [104], [123], [132], [149], [172]–[174], [180], [219]–[221], [223], [227], [232], [277], [344], [350], [370], [444]	[28], [41], [53], [87], [96], [132], [172]–[174], [219], [223], [232], [241], [256]	[28], [45], [53], [73], [75], [87], [96], [172], [173], [223], [232], [244], [256], [344], [440]	[30], [35], [41], [104], [221], [232], [241], [244], [256], [370]	[21], [53], [219], [221], [232], [241], [256], [440]	[41], [45], [53], [221], [223], [241], [244], [440]	[104], [223]
	Fuzzy	[18], [19], [48]–[50], [52], [60], [62], [69], [70], [97], [111], [114], [117], [141], [143], [150], [160], [161], [218], [233], [243], [258], [275], [358], [360], [369], [370], [402], [419], [428]	[62], [70], [97], [150], [218], [258], [275], [327], [358], [419], [428]	[49], [62], [69], [70], [160], [258], [275], [358], [419], [428]	[50], [141], [161], [218], [233], [243], [370], [441]	[218], [233], [337], [402]	[233], [327]	[50]
Meta-heuristic	[35], [38], [40], [41], [50], [61], [99], [101], [107], [119], [147], [150], [162], [164], [181], [272], [325], [332], [358], [361], [369], [376], [377], [387], [389], [393]	[23], [38], [40], [41], [119], [147], [150], [162], [272], [325], [332], [358], [361], [377], [387], [389], [393]	[40], [162], [181], [325], [358], [387], [389]	[35], [41], [50], [99], [101], [387], [389]	[23], [38]	[41]	[50], [101], [361]	
Engineering-based	[54], [115], [138], [168], [176], [218], [231], [235], [249], [262], [268], [283], [285], [286], [289], [334], [367], [403], [405], [427], [436]	[53]–[55], [218], [235], [239], [241], [256], [262], [283], [334], [394], [398], [400], [405], [422], [424], [425], [427], [436], [448], [449]	[53], [231], [239], [244], [256], [290], [424], [440]	[54], [72], [82], [176], [183], [218], [237], [241], [244], [256], [289], [334], [367], [381], [403], [449]	[20], [53], [55], [115], [145], [183], [218], [235], [237], [239], [241], [249], [256], [262], [289], [290], [331], [337], [346], [349], [363], [394], [398], [400], [403], [405], [422], [424], [427], [429], [432], [440], [448]–[452]	[20], [53], [55], [237], [241], [244], [285], [290], [394], [440], [449], [451]	[183], [239]	

4.3 Spatiotemporal level of detail

The spatial and temporal properties represent the level of detail applied within the articles and are a common decision criteria for model selection. The level of detail of available input data also substantially influences the resolution and scale of the output of a model. Figure 8 summarizes the core findings with regards to the applied techniques.

Figure 8: Relative share of category of techniques by temporal horizon and temporal and spatial resolution. Left: Relative share of categorized techniques by temporal horizon. ML and metaheuristic techniques are predominantly employed for short-term projections while engineering-based approaches are used for longer timeframes. Middle: Relative share of categorized techniques by temporal resolution. There is an overall tendency towards hourly time steps. Techniques are used equally across all temporal resolutions, except ML, which decrease for longer time-steps. Right: Relative share of categorized techniques by spatial resolution. Buildings, households and regions are analyzed the most. Engineering-based models stand out in showing a clear tendency towards high level of detail.

The analysis of the temporal horizon (Figure 8, left) reveals an overall higher number of occurrences for short- (<= 1 day) and long-term (>= 1 year) projections compared to medium-term. It is shown that ML techniques are applied more frequently for short temporal horizons while engineering-based and uncertainty techniques are used more often for longer time frames. This is in line with a common view within scientific literature, whereby engineering-based energy demand models are described as simulation approaches, which are suitable for modelling longer time spans in a realistic and reliable manner [435]. For the other approaches, there seems to be no particular tendency. A detailed analysis with regards to input data shows that the usage of weather and calendar data is decreasing for long term predictions while the usage of demographic, economic and price data is increasing.

The analysis of the temporal resolution (Figure 8, middle) reveals an overall tendency towards hourly time steps or shorter. In particular, hourly time steps represent a reasonable compromise between level of detail, availability and data quantity for most projects, since an hourly resolution allows to represent most human-driven impacts on consumption, such as daily routines, while the amount of data is still manageable. Additionally, a lot of weather and consumption data is tracked at least in hourly time steps. However, there are differences among the energy carriers: for example, there was no article that modelled natural gas consumption with shorter than hourly time steps. The difference in temporal resolution for electricity and gas most likely reflects system operation requirements and the respective metering infrastructure [437]. Figure 8 also shows that all techniques are used across temporal resolutions from sub hourly to daily. For time steps longer than one day, there is a decrease of ML approaches while statistical approaches are used more frequently. We expect no clear trend among the techniques here, since the size of the time steps should not favor the usage of a particular technique. When analyzing input data, it is revealed that there is a higher proportion of demographic

and economic data as well as energy prices for longer than daily time steps, which goes along with predicting longer temporal horizons.

The investigation on the spatial resolution (Figure 8, right) shows an overall tendency of modelling energy consumption on the level of single households and buildings or on regional level, e. g. on a district-scale. Comparatively fewer approaches focus on the level of appliances or on national consumption. Engineering-based techniques stand out in having a clear tendency towards the building and appliance level, reflecting the high level of detail which is characteristic for this technique. Scaling an engineering-based model to the national level requires high amounts of detailed technical system data, which has only been done in few cases [296] (see Table 9). In contrast, statistical techniques are used most frequently on large geographic scales, reflecting their traditional role in econometric analyses. Consequently, the technical system and behavioral data is especially important for smaller scales, in which demographic and economic data is almost never used.

Table 8 represents a compilation of the techniques and level of detail per article. The table can be used to identify recent articles that share a similar combination of these properties, which enables anybody to quickly find matching articles for their own projects.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

Table 8: Techniques and level of detail per article. Compiled results of the analysis on techniques, temporal horizon and spatial resolution. Table follows a matrix structure: Within each category of techniques all articles referenced within a cell rely on the category specified by the corresponding row and the input data specified by the column.

Technique	Tempora l horizon	Spatial Resolution			
		Appliance	Building/household	Regional	National
Machine- Learning	Short	[46], [85], [131], [150], [275], [280], [418]	[41], [60], [107], [109], [112], [148], [153], [222], [223], [226], [238], [251], [255], [257], [264], [269], [274], [276], [278], [284], [297], [303], [308], [312], [313], [316], [317], [319], [320], [324], [326], [328], [332], [343], [351], [358], [388], [390], [393], [401], [414], [443], [445]	[38], [59], [61], [66], [69], [76], [84], [86], [94], [102], [105], [110], [111], [132], [133], [135], [136], [146], [162], [163], [166], [167], [177], [192], [200], [209], [214], [215], [230], [265], [372], [376], [382], [392], [395], [397], [411], [453]	[19], [70], [180], [181], [204], [212], [213], [348], [362], [368]
	Medium	[261], [288], [432]	[228], [236], [248], [258], [293], [304], [315], [336], [339], [340], [353], [385], [387], [399], [404], [407], [420], [428], [442]	[34], [68], [97], [98], [126], [139], [152], [165], [169], [182], [219], [225], [341], [365], [366], [391], [417], [454]	[65], [113], [127], [129], [147]
	Long		[64], [203], [234], [262], [263], [295], [338], [419], [423]	[22], [35], [49], [62], [67], [83], [141], [154], [186], [195], [198], [202], [206], [211], [224], [271], [300], [321], [371], [455]	[30], [50], [52], [79], [80], [120], [121], [124], [151], [158], [161], [191], [199], [199], [205], [210], [357], [374]
Statistical	Short	[78], [131], [253], [350], [355]	[60], [112], [148], [217], [229], [238], [242], [242], [247], [251], [255], [281], [284], [294], [303], [309]–[314], [319], [326], [332], [401]	[31], [69], [74], [93], [110], [130], [149], [157], [162], [163], [175], [177], [265], [277], [378], [380], [382], [392], [395]	[70], [95], [96], [137], [178], [180], [187], [201], [213], [237], [348]
	Medium	[288], [323], [352]	[17], [218], [227], [236], [245], [246], [248], [252], [306], [315], [339], [345], [387], [431]	[108], [118], [125], [139], [143], [169], [171], [318], [447], [456]	[65], [103], [104], [113], [114], [127], [129], [384]
	Long	[235]	[216], [233], [240], [250], [273], [298], [329], [338], [344], [403], [423]	[48], [49], [83], [91], [116], [122], [141], [142], [155], [156], [159], [185], [186], [188], [193], [194], [198], [224], [266], [307], [318], [321], [325], [375], [455]	[30], [77], [80], [81], [89], [92], [99], [120], [121], [128], [144], [151], [158], [161], [189], [196], [205], [207], [208], [260], [279], [286], [369], [370], [373], [374], [379], [383], [386], [446]
Stochastic/ Fuzzy/Grey	Short	[46], [150], [275], [350]	[21], [41], [47], [53], [60], [221], [223], [242], [308], [309], [358]	[31], [69], [111], [132], [149], [190], [277], [372]	[19], [70], [96], [123], [180], [212]
	Medium		[218], [220], [227], [258], [301], [428]	[34], [97], [143], [219], [341], [456]	[104], [114]
	Long		[216], [233], [256], [298], [344], [415], [419]	[35], [48], [49], [62], [141], [216], [241], [243], [271]	[18], [30], [50], [52], [160], [161], [369], [370], [373], [440]
Meta- heuristic	Short	[150]	[41], [107], [303], [332], [343], [358], [377], [393]	[38], [61], [162], [215], [376]	[181]
	Medium		[387]	[119]	[147]
	Long			[35], [325]	[50], [99], [101], [369]
Engineering -based	Short	[145], [331], [346], [425], [450]	[53], [115], [239], [413]		[237]
	Medium	[432], [448]	[20], [218], [398], [422], [436], [452]	[138]	[283]
	Long	[235], [290], [400], [451]	[55], [249], [256], [262], [403], [415], [424], [449]	[72], [82], [168], [176], [183], [241], [289], [381], [405]	[296]

4.4 Prediction accuracy

Prediction accuracy has a direct relationship with decision quality [69]. Therefore the pursuit of performance enhancement and higher levels of accuracy is one of the driving factors of the development of new techniques and combinations among them. Given its importance, researchers might consider the forecasting accuracy as a criterion for model selection. According to Hong and Fan, the most used performance measure in the electric power industry is MAPE, due to its simplicity and transparency [3]. Lewis' benchmark [457], which has been mentioned by several authors [18], [458], suggests, that a MAPE value of 10% or lower suggests high prediction accuracy.

Modeling energy demand – A systematic literature review

In several literature reviews MAPE values of different techniques are compared and some tendencies could be identified [2], [14], [24]. Debnath and Mourshed suggested, that ML and hybrid approaches tend to perform more accurate compared to other techniques [2] and Wei et al. found that MAPE values of long-term projections tend to be better than for short-term projections [14]. However, other authors are reluctant to give clear recommendations, stating that the different choice of performance measures made it hard to categorize the methods from best to worst [2, p. 310] and the suitability of models finally depend on the dataset [24, p. 26].

MAPE was the most frequently used accuracy measure among articles and was provided in 217 of 419 cases. Other measures like root mean square error (RMSE), normalized RMSE (nRMSE), mean absolute error (MAE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) were encountered in several cases as well.

Figure 9 shows that a direct comparison does not reveal a universal higher level of accuracy for any technique. While engineering-based methods have a slightly higher median (green line), the means (red diamonds) are almost equal among all techniques. This could be due to the great variety of available approaches within each category, allowing users to find techniques which are tailored to their use-cases. Furthermore, for every technique particular measures and sub-routines have been developed to counter drawbacks and increase accuracy (see section 4.5).

Figure 9: Boxplot of MAPE values by categories of techniques. Box represents the interquartile range (IQR). Whiskers show range of data beyond 1st and 3rd quartile and extend until 1.5*IQR on each side, ending at maximum and minimum data points within that interval. Outliers are not shown. Green line represents median. Red diamond represents mean. Accuracy measured by MAPE does not seem to depend necessarily on the chosen technique.

Figure 10: Boxplot of MAPE values by spatial levels of detail. Same mode of display as in Figure 9. Shows that higher detail results in lower accuracy. This is because aggregated loads on country and regional level are smoother and have stronger temporal patterns compared to loads of individual appliances or households, which are subject to behavioral patterns, which are subject to a higher degree of randomness.

Figure 10 shows evidence, that use-cases indeed have an influence on the accuracy. However, it is not the temporal horizon or the temporal resolution which revealed a clear tendency (see Figure 11 and Figure 12 in

the appendix), but the spatial resolution. Higher details proved to result in higher MAPE values. Hence, the prediction of loads of individual appliances provided the lowest level of accuracy and highest variance as well. The explanation is twofold. On the one hand, aggregated loads on the level of countries or regions are smoother and more likely to show seasonal or trend-related patterns compared to loads of individual appliances, households or industrial processes. This is because, disaggregated loads depend on the behavior of users and their routines and have a higher degree of randomness, which naturally produces lower degrees of accuracy in their prediction. On the other hand, historic datasets of disaggregated consumption are more scarcely available. Hence, techniques, which closely fit to historic data are employed less frequently and bottom-up techniques, which derive profiles from time-use data and rated power of appliances are used.

4.5 Measures for improvement of accuracy

Techniques have become more flexible over the years to be adapted to the specific contexts and datasets in which they are used and particular sub-routines have been developed to counter drawbacks and improve predictive performance.

For ML techniques, the following measures to improve predictive performance have been undertaken. To reduce overfitting, ensemble learning was employed to create independent predictions of multiple models and use weighted averaged results [60], [65], [69], [94], [138], [224], [274], [321], [336], [357], [370], [420], [446]. Other measures against overfitting include the usage of incremental learning and dynamic neural networks, where the models are updated step by step during training phase [63], [66], [111], [321] or restrictions on weights [162] as well as the introduction of dropout layers [328]. To boost accuracy stacked auto encoders were used [22], [133], [280], [444] as well as using long short-term memory (LSTM) networks [148], [192], [206], [365], [417]. Another measure to increase accuracy for ANN is to vary the number of neurons and layers which has been done in [66], [170], [316], [423].

The curse of dimensionality [105] is a common problem, which occurs when dealing with high dimensional datasets. Elimination of insignificant features and appropriate selection is crucial for ML and regression techniques. This was achieved by using correlation and principal component analyses (PCA) in [100], [116], [325], [327], [335], [338], [348], [365], [401], [418], [93], [136], [229], [250], [310], [423]. For ML approaches feature selection was also done by genetic algorithms and decision trees in [40], [41], [68], [165] and fuzzy based feature selection in [112], [150], [275]. In the case of regression techniques, the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) was used [121], [177], [186], [187].

Another popular measure is the preprocessing of data in order to eliminate outliers and noise, as well as isolate seasonal [69] or temperature related [230] patterns. For TSA ML techniques this has been done by using wavelet or Fourier transformation in [40], [59], [67], [68], [98], [132], [193], [393] and [80], [81], [313], [345]. Particular attention was paid to the prediction of special events and holidays in [70], [92], [137], [395].

Sometimes model performance suffers from the lack of data. In the case of ML approaches this can be compensated by the creation of virtual data through densification or latent information functions [73], [184]. In engineering-based techniques insufficient data can be tackled by prioritization as well as the right choice of representative samples as done in [20], [55], [115], [405], [452].

ML approaches sometimes suffer from ending up in local shallow minima when optimizing parameters. The solutions can involve the inclusion of alternative (metaheuristic) optimization routines during training stage, such as artificial bee colony algorithm for ANN [99], [376] or the Cuckoo search [61] or wolf pack algorithm [150] for SVM.

5 Discussion

The analysis has shown that energy demand modelling is a research field with continuous high numbers of yearly publications. Most articles focus on electricity consumption, which is not surprising since it is the most valuable and expensive form of energy. Moreover, due to service level requirements of grid infrastructure and expansion of smart meters, vast amounts of detailed and high-quality data is available, especially in the hands of grid operators. However, we expect an increasing number of smart metering devices also in the gas and heat grids, which will improve data availability in the future and facilitate integrated energy system planning and modelling.

Studies with a focus on buildings represent a significant overall share among articles and are particularly relevant in the context of modelling heating and cooling demand in the residential and commercial sector. In comparison, the industry sector is underrepresented in the sample of articles. On the background of the intense efforts regarding efficiency targets and demand side management potentials, there is a large interest in modeling the industry sector. However, the small number of articles shows a lack of publicly available data as well as the reluctance to publish this kind of research. This might be, because energy consumption of a company is considered sensitive data since it implicitly contains information about production activity and efficiency.

ML techniques are used the most across the articles and showed an increase in usage over the last years. ML has the advantages of being able to handle nonlinear relations and achieve high levels of accuracy with quite low implementation effort [23]. Drawbacks lie in the black-box character [101], the tendency of overfitting and getting stuck at shallow local minima [147], [376]. Countermeasures are the formation of model ensembles as well as feature selection and data preprocessing by decomposition. ML techniques dominate across all temporal and spatial levels, however with a slight tendency towards smaller time steps, horizons and scales.

Statistical modelling techniques have a long history in econometrics but are common in energy demand modelling and are the second most used technique. Multiple linear regression is fast and simple to use and capable of explaining the relationship between independent and dependent variables. However, when independent variables are correlated, these models face difficulties [100]. One way of counteracting is by refining variable selection process and reducing complexity with the help of PCA or LASSO. TSA techniques also are easy to use and efficient in modelling overall trend and seasonal patterns. Limits occur with when it comes to forecasting extreme events or outliers. Countermeasures can be found in the transformation and decomposition of data [375].

Techniques for stochastic, fuzzy and grey systems modelling address different types of uncertainty. As discussed by Hong and Fan [3, pp. 915, 936], having elements of uncertainty included in model outputs can be considered to be unsatisfying for decision makers in management positions who expect single point values. However, this branch of energy demand modelling can still be considered as a recent development, which will likely see an increase in popularity over the next years. Fuzzy and grey approaches are able to deal with incomplete or inaccurate data [97], [369]. Stochastic simulations might run into long computing times, which can be countered by variable elimination algorithms [223].

Meta-heuristic approaches are mainly used as part of combined models, e.g. by introducing genetic feature selection algorithms [41], [358] or by optimizing model parameters through an evolutionary process [99], [164], [181]. However, the integration of a metaheuristic algorithm into another technique represents an advanced model set-up which requires additional knowledge and effort, which has to be justified by improved results.

Engineering-based techniques derive energy demand from a bottom-up representation, which involves a detailed representation of input-output-relationships based on the laws of physics. This level of detail represents a fundamental difference to the other techniques. Engineering-based techniques are commonly used in the context of building simulation [58], [400]. However, the requirement of large amounts of parameters

as well as the accurate representation of input-output relationships make the initial set-up of such a model rather laborious. Once created, however, these models have the potential to predict different scenarios on a long temporal horizon, which makes them particularly relevant in the context of system planning. Furthermore, the forecasting based on historic data, as done by ML and TSA techniques, is unable to depict structural disruptions, such as the consequences of political interventions, technological breakthroughs or a pandemic.

Accuracy of prediction is one of the most important factors in decision making, not only to allow the right choice of models but also to allow stakeholders to understand the performance of the employed method. Unlike other authors [2], [14] a tendency of higher accuracy for ML and hybrid techniques or for longer temporal horizons could not be confirmed. However, it was shown that models with higher spatial detail have a tendency towards lower accuracy. This shows that comparing MAPE values of techniques irrespective of the individual context in which they are applied is of limited explanatory value. In order to robustly compare and discuss accuracy of different techniques they have to be applied to the same datasets, as done in forecasting competitions, such as GEFCom [459].

6 Conclusion

In this article a comprehensive and up-to-date systematic literature review about recent trends in energy demand modelling regarding techniques, data, accuracy, energy carriers, sectors and spatiotemporal level of detail. References are compiled in tables for easy access and structured by property.

The analysis of the articles proved the current trend of increasing popularity for ML approaches. Statistical models such as regression and TSA are well established and stochastic/fuzzy/grey and metaheuristic techniques often are used as part of combined approaches. Engineering-based techniques stand out as they provide a more detailed representation of the physical properties of the energy consuming system. This is also reflected in their data requirements which is based less on historic energy demand but more so on technical system data and other external information.

Modeling and forecasting accuracy proves to be a difficult criterion for ranking of techniques, since attainable performance depends on the particular context. In fact, higher details, e.g. forecasting on the level of appliances, produced lower levels of accuracy compared to forecasts of aggregated loads on regional or country levels. A research gap was identified regarding models for industrial energy demand.

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7 References

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P. Verwiebe, S. Seim, S. Burges, J. Müller-Kirchenbauer

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Appendix

A.1. Existing literature reviews

Table 9: Characteristics of existing literature reviews. Overview of existing literature reviews by content. In each line black squares indicate topics covered in the given review. Only seven literatures used a systematic approach. Most reviews cover more than one sector or energy carrier and are concerned with analyzing model inputs (demand drivers). Few reviews show the number of articles reviewed. Only the present article covers all aspects.

Systematic	Energy carriers				Sectors					Building focused	Demand drivers	Reviewed articles	Reference
	Electricity	Thermal	Natural gas	Primary energy	Residential	Commercial	Industries	Transportation	General				
■	■								■		■	41	[9]
■	■	■			■						■	n/a	[11]
■	■	■			■	■	■			■	■	63	[10]
■	■	■	■	■					■			483	[2]
■	■	■			■	■	■					130	[12]
■	■		■		■	■					■	39	[13]
■	■	■	■	■					■		■	116	[14]
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>													
	■	■							■		■	n/a	[460]
	■				■	■	■			■		n/a	[461]
			■				■					n/a	[462]
	■				■	■				■	■	31	[463]
	■								■		■	n/a	[3]
	■								■			n/a	[464]
	■				■	■	■				■	50	[24]
	■				■						■	n/a	[465]
	■					■			■		■	n/a	[466]
	■						■				■	n/a	[467]
	■							■				n/a	[468]
		■							■	■		n/a	[469]
	■	■							■	■		n/a	[470]
	■	■			■	■			■		■	n/a	[471]
	■	■			■				■			n/a	[472]
	■	■		■	■	■	■		■	■	■	n/a	[458]
	■	■			■				■		■	n/a	[473]
	■	■			■	■			■			n/a	[474]
	■	■			■	■	■		■			n/a	[475]
			■								■	17	[476]
	■											n/a	[477]
				■							■	n/a	[478], [479]
■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	419	This review

A.2. Figures

Figure 11: Boxplot of MAPE values by different temporal resolutions. Same mode of display as in Figure 9. Shows that temporal resolution (length of time steps) does not seem to necessarily have an impact on accuracy measured by MAPE.

Figure 12: Boxplot of MAPE values by different temporal horizons. Same mode of display as in Figure 9. Shows that length of temporal horizon does not seem to necessarily have an impact on accuracy measured by MAPE.

Figure 13: Technical systems analyzed. Shows that most articles focus on power grid and buildings.